

Subjective level of distress and psychological well-being of selected SDCA students: Basis for guidance and counseling intervention

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Abstract

This research utilized the Descriptive-Correlational methods of research. It was participated by 168 students who were requested to answer two on-line instruments namely Subjective Unit of Distress and Ryff's Psychological Well-being scale. The purpose of the study is to know the level of distress as pre-counseling assessment and to find out if there is linear correlation between subjective distress and psychological well-being of the participants. Findings of the study include 1) participants' level of subjective distress is moderate ($X=46.10$) 2) overall well-being is average ($X=55$) and lastly, there is no linear correlation between subjective distress and well-being ($t\ 0.25 < 0.80$). Factors of Psychological well-being that are regarded as "Possible Strengths" are 1) Positive Relations (5.04) and Personal Growth (5.08) while factors Self-Acceptance (2.58) and Environmental Mystery (2.76) are regarded as Areas of Concern.

Keywords: Subjective unit of distress. Psychological well-being.

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Introduction

The motivation to conduct our present study is because of the need to know the current level of distress of students seeking help related to their mental health. The use of pre-assessment instruments such as Depression Inventory (Beck, 1961) and Subjective Unit of Distress (Wolpe, 1969) as one of the baseline information helps in the conduct of counseling services. Because of the effective utilization of the ratings of Subjective Unit of Distress (60 up means higher level of subjective distress) and explanations ("I tend to overthink, restless and more anxious"; "I cannot take care of myself, I am losing control") as initial assessment provided by students-clients, the researchers agreed to administer Joseph Wolpe's Subjective Unit of Distress Scale (1969) to larger number of students to identify those who are in need of further and urgent counseling intervention.

The second mover in the conceptualization of the above-mentioned title of our research is connected to the duration of emotional experience of distress and what will happen to their psychological well-being. Robertson (n.d.) posited that if one's daily circumstances are consistently distressing, even the most resilient individual may eventually feel quite low, or depressed. He added that long-term exposure to work-related stressors has a detrimental impact on psychological well-being. Highly significant is the contribution of Coronavirus disease causing a new range of stressors that threaten people's health, safety, and economic, and well-being in general (Bridgland et al., 2021). For instance, students and workers alike are overwhelmed by co-existence or unclear boundaries between studies and household chores among students and work as employees and parenting/household responsibilities among parents. Prolonged and significant stressors brought by Covid-19 may increase stress exponentially, which will eventually have a negative impact to psychological well-being (Johnson et al., 2018).

For these reasons, if research will be done, several benefits are projected. One, the administration and the result of Subjective Unit of Distress (SUDS) is a gauge of SDCA students' current and intensity of emotional experience of distress useful in the onset of counseling. Second, the utilization of Ryff's Subjective State of Well-being is for profiling of students that will reveal the status of the 6 factors of the instrument namely 1) autonomy, 2) environmental mastery, 3) personal growth, 4) positive relations with others, 5) purpose in life and 6) self-acceptance will also aid the Student and Wellness Unit in devising the content of intervention programs, and thirdly, to test the contention of Cooper, that is, long-term exposure to stressors has a negative impact on psychological well-being.

Kiyimba and O'Reilly (2020) conducted an exploratory study entitled "The Clinical Use of Subjective Unit of Distress Scales (SUDs) in Child Mental Health Assessments: A Thematic Evaluation". The study explores the use of the SUDS analogue rating scale in initial mental health assessment. To investigate the specific interactional application of SUDS, the theme analysis method was applied.

The researchers discovered four themes: recency, longevity, context, and miscommunication. The child's emotional score on the scale was supplemented by the first three themes. The need for clarity when using SUDS with children and young people was emphasized by the theme of miscommunication. The researchers recommended utilizing the rating scales in clinical assessment.

A research study by Winefield et al. (2012) utilized two variables namely, psychological distress and psychological well-being. She found out that Psychological distress was inversely related with factors that were positively associated with psychological well-being and vice versa. When psychological well-being is low and psychological distress is low it is associated with negative life conditions such as being separated, having no educational qualification, unemployed. Researcher concluded that psychological well-being is not yet at the other end of the spectrum from psychological distress.

Azañedo et al. (2020) conducted a research on the social intelligence and psychological distress with Subjective well-being and psychological well-being as mediators. To quantify the direct influence of social intelligence on psychopathological symptoms, as well as its indirect effect through its impacts on subjective and psychological well-being components, a multiple mediation model was proposed. Social intelligence was found to be favorably and significantly linked to psychological well-being, with significant positive and negative indirect impacts on psychological distress through the dimension of positive interpersonal relationships. The researchers viewed the result as a contribution in expanding the explanatory models of the influence on social intelligence on mental health and in designing interventions based on the strength of social intelligence for the promotion of well-being and the reduction in psychological distress.

Theoretical Framework

This paper was guided by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman's theory of stress stating that stress is referred to as the mismatch between the expectations placed on an individual and the individual's resources to cope (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Such contention is well elaborated by Robertson (n.d.) who posited that even the most resilient person may eventually become very low, or depressed, if his or her daily experiences are constantly troubling, like that of being amid uncertainty caused by pandemic. He added that work-related stressors over long periods of time will have a negative impact on psychological well-being.

Another theory of stress is by Hans Selye which he called the theory of General Adaptation Syndrome (GAS) in 1951. He based his theory on physiology and psychobiology, stating an event that threatens an individual's being well-being or stressors lead to a three-stage bodily responses namely Alarm, Resistance, and Exhaustion.

The above-mentioned theories explain how environment demands and prolong exposure to it impacted one's personal feelings and psychological well-being.

Statement of the Problem

Problem 1: What is the profile of selected SDCA students as revealed by their responses in two instruments namely Subjective unit of distress (SUDS) and Ryff's Psychological Well-being?

Specifically, Problem 1 intended to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of subjective distress?
2. What is the respondents' general/overall level of psychological well-being? Level per area/factor of Ryff's Psychological well-being test?
3. What is the level of respondents' psychological well-being, when grouped according to courses?
4. What are the low scoring items of psychological well-being which may reveal possible concerns and high scoring items which can be regarded as possible strengths of the respondents?

Problem 2: To find out if subjective level of distress is correlated with psychological being.

Hypothesis of the Study

Ho: There is no significant correlation between subjective unit of distress and psychological wellbeing of SDCA students.

Significance of the Study

To SDCA Students. The present study benefited the students specifically those who scored high in Subjective of Unit Distress Scale and with written explanations for the rating that are alarming were contacted, counseled, and followed up.

To Student Wellness Office. The result of the study can be used as content of their guidance intervention especially the respondents high score or ratings in subjective unit of distress and low scores in each factor or areas of Ryff's psychological well-being scale.

To Academic Community. The result of the study can be used in providing necessary adjustments in terms of teaching and learning strategies, volume of requirements and time management.

Methodology

This research is a simple descriptive-correlational research method.

Research Participants

Participants were 167 college students at St Dominic College of Asia. Majority of the participants are graduating students taking Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology (BSRT), Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSTM), Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Science in Psychology (BSPSY), Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy (BSPH), Bachelor in Multimedia Arts (BMMA), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT), Bachelor in Secondary Education (BSED), and Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA).

Sampling Procedure

The researchers utilized the convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling which is defined as sampling that involves using respondents who are convenient to the researcher (Galloway, 2005). In this research, the classes handled by one of the researchers were utilized as respondents. The two instruments were administered via Google Forms.

Research Instruments

Subjective Unit of Distress (SUD, Joseph Wolpe, 1969) also called subjective units of disturbance, is a 0 to 100 scale for determining the subjective intensity of disturbance or distress that an individual is currently experiencing. Higher ratings mean higher level of subjective distress. Below are the ratings and the corresponding descriptions:

0	Totally relaxed
10	Alert, awake, concentrating well
20	Minimal anxiety/distress
30	Mild anxiety/distress, no interference with performance
40-60	Moderate anxiety/distress, uncomfortable, but can continue to perform
70	Quite anxious/distress, interfering with performance
80	Very anxious/distress, can't concentrate
90	Extremely anxious/distress
100	Highest distress/fear/anxiety/discomfort

The researchers chose SUDS because it is commonly used in assessment and proven useful tool for establishing current level of distress in children and young people. Before the conceptualization of our research topic, SUDS was used by the researchers as tool to identify the level of distress of students seeking counseling SUDS is quick to administer and easy to understand for all age groups (Cigrang et al., 2017).

Ryff's Psychological Well-being

Ryff's Scales of Psychological Well-being (Carol Ryff, 2007;1989) is a 42-item Psychological Wellbeing (PWB) Scale that measures six aspects of well-being and happiness namely 1) autonomy, 2) environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life and self-acceptance. Low scores are considered some problematic areas (or area of concern) while high scores are regarded as possible strengths.

Statistical Treatment

Percentage (%)

This will be used to clearly show how many/much is the shared value of each level of subjective unit of distress rated in 100 percent. This is by dividing the score of each subjective level of distress to the total respondents then multiply the result with 100 (obtained score divide by total score x 100). In this research, percentage is used to get how many respondents in each level of Subjective unit of distress scale shared in 100 percent.

Statistical Mean (X)

It is defined as the average or the most common value in the collection of numbers. Mean is obtained through adding all of the data set's values and then dividing by the number of values added. In this research, the statistical mean is used to determine the overall or general level psychological well-being of the respondents, as well as the most common value in each factor or areas of psychological well-being.

Pearson-r test of Correlation

It is used to test if there is a linear relationship between subjective distress and psychological well-being.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: What is the profile of selected SDCA students as revealed by their responses in two instruments namely Subjective unit of distress (SUDS) and Ryff's Psychological Well-being?

Table 1. Level of distress of selected SDCA students

Respondents N=167	Percentage	Rating	Interpretation
0	0.00	0	Totally Relaxed
3	1.79	10	Alert and Awake, Concentrating
17	10.17	20	Minimal Anxiety, distress
25	14.97	30	Mild distress/No interference to
77	46.10	40-60	Moderate anxiety, uncomfortable
27	16.16	70	Quite anxiety, can interfere to per-
11	6.58	80	Very anxious, can't concentrate
4	2.39	90	Extremely anxious
3	1.79	100	Highest distress, fear and anxious
TOTAL	100.00		

Table 1 shows the level of distress of the respondents. With the nine levels of subjective unit of distress scale, the most rated levels are as follows: the highest number of respondents or 77 students are *moderate* in their distress between 40-60 (46.19 percent) that means students are feeling uncomfortable but they can continue to perform. Next is 27 students rated their distress 70 (16.16 percent) which is "quite *high level of anxiety*", a level of distress that can interfere significantly to their performance while 25 students rated their distress 30 (14.97 percent) which is interpreted as "*mild* distress with no interference to performance".

Non-problematic level of distress is rated by 17 students 20 (10.17 percent) categorized as minimal anxiety and 3 students rather themselves 10 described as "alert and awake level, comprising only 1.79 percent.

However, three levels must be given considerable attention, they are the very anxious (11 students; 58 percent) extremely anxious (4 students; 2.39 percent) and highest distress (3 students; 1.79 percent).

Table 2. General level of psychological well-being and level per area/factor of Ryff's Psychological Well-being test

Areas of Psychological Well-being	Mean Score	Interpretation
Autonomy	53	Average
Environmental Mastery	53	Average
Personal Growth	61	High
Positive Relations	57	High
Purpose in Life	56	Average
Self-Acceptance	52	Average
Total	332 (X=55)	Average

Table 2 shows the general level of psychological well-being of the 167 respondents, which is 332 with mean score of 55 classified as average level of psychological well-being. With regards with the 6 factors of Ryff's Psychological well-being scale, the respondents mean scores are classified average on 4 factors namely Autonomy, Environmental mystery, Purpose in life and Self-acceptance. While factors Personal Growth and Positive Relations are interpreted as high with mean scores of 61 and 57 respectively.

Table 3. Respondents' level of overall psychological well-being when grouped according to course

Course	Respondents	Level of Psychological Well-being	Interpretation
BSED	1	409	High
BSIT	4	293	Average
BSHM	9	330	Average
BSN	25	355	High
BACOMM	2	315	Average
BSA	40	336	High
BMMA	1	284	Average
BSBA	23	349	High
BSTM	7	307	Average
BSP	7	318	Average
BSPT	3	328	Average
BSPSY	30	320	Average
BSRT	15	341	High

Table 3 shows the respondents' level of psychological well-being when grouped according to course. Courses which psychological being is high are from Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA), Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), Bachelor of Science in Radiologic Technology (BSRT) and Bachelor in Secondary Education (BSED). The remaining eight courses are average; they are Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT), Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Arts in Communication (BACOMM), Bachelor in Multimedia Arts (BMMA), Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSTM), Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy (BSP), Bachelor of Science in Physical Therapy (BSPT) and Bachelor of Science in Psychology (BSPSY).

Table 4. Possible strengths and possible areas of concerns

Possible Strengths	Possible Areas of Concern
<p>1. Positive Relations "It is important to me to be a good listener when close friends talk to me about their problems." (5.04)</p> <p>2. Personal Growth "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing and growth." (5.08)</p>	<p>1. Self-Acceptance "Given the opportunity, there are many things about myself that I would change." (2.58)</p> <p>2. Environmental Mastery "I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities." (2.76)</p>

Table 4 shows specific items in four areas or factors of psychological well-being scale. They are categorized into Areas of Concern referring to low-scored factors of Ryff's Psychological well-being and Possible Strengths referring to high scored items of the instrument used.

The respondents' high mean scores in factors Positive Relations (5.04) specifically in the statement "It is important to me to be a good listener when close friends talk to me about their problems" reveals the participants' willingness to be engaged in meaningful and nurturing relations with others. Positive relations are regarded as foundation of mental health and well-being, specifically, it can help people live longer and happier with few mental health problems. In addition, positive relationships can give a person a sense of purpose and sense of belonging (Edwards et al., 2016).

Another area where the participants scored noticeably high is Personal Growth (5.08), specifically the item "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing and growth" manifests the participants' welcoming response to new experiences and recognizes improvement in behavior and self-overtime.

The area of concern where the participants scored noticeably low are Self-acceptance (2.58) specifically the item "Given the opportunity, there are many things about myself that I would change". Another low-scored factor is Environmental Mastery (2.76), described as the ability to efficiently manage one's life and environment (Ryff, 1995), specifically the item "I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities". Possible reasons for this are the demands of academic as revealed by participants that they are experiencing high distress related to online learning ("on-line learning is draining my brain"; not really understand the lessons; "severe stress due to on-line class"; "feeling lazy"; "I tend to procrastinate"; "could not perform schoolwork"). There are participants who revealed that they were also coerced to do part time job to augment their needs.

Table 5. Correlation between SUDS and Psychological Well-being

Autonomy	Environmental Mastery	Personal Growth	Positive Relations	Purpose in Life	Self-Acceptance	Overall Well-being
0.03	0.03	-0.02	-0.02	0.05	0.02	r=0.02
0.36	0.43	0.19	-0.22	0.69	0.23	t value 0.25
0.72	0.67	0.85	0.83	0.49	0.82	p value 0.80
Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept Null Hypothesis

Table 5 shows that there is no linear relation between Subjective distress and overall well-being of the participants, with 0.02 correlation coefficient (r) value and the p-value of 0.80. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This finding is consistent with the conclusion of Winefield et al. (2012) that psychological well-being is not quite the opposite end of the spectrum to psychological distress.

With regards to the subjective distress of the respondents, the moderate level of anxiety or distress, with description, "even though uncomfortable but can continue to perform" (40-60) is the highest in percentage (77 respondents = 46.10%).

However, the brief explanations of their rating shows 1) low level of motivation (feeling lazy, procrastination, could not perform school work), 2) high distress related to on-line learning (on-line learning is draining my brain, not really understand the lessons, severe stress due to on-line class), and 3) alarming disturbances (sudden burst of stress, overthinking, sleepless nights, personal worries, too much negative thoughts, deep seated negative feelings, disappointment). Seventy-seven (77) respondents attributed their moderate stress to the following: pandemic (26), online learning or demands of school work (28), parents' unemployment/financial problem (11), multiple responsibilities (5), upcoming graduation (3), while the remaining 23% wrote about their social anxiety, too much anticipation of future, and growing sense of isolation. The details provided in the respondents' explanations of their numerical rating are "good baselines in counseling encounter" (Kiyimba & O'Reilly, 2020). While their numerical rating is on moderate level, their explanations show significant crisis level that necessitates urgent counseling intervention.

The total of 45 respondents who quantify their distress as Quite anxious (27), Very anxious (11), Extremely anxious (4) and Highest distress (3) gave explanations which are considered normal responses to intense triggers such as studying while working (8), broken family (2) and financial problem due to pandemic (7). But the rest revealed more serious conditions such as "experiencing panic attack manifested in hyper arousal, chest tight, stomach is fluttering easily get frightened, could not take care of myself", "source of high level of distress is not identified", losing control of myself, my life is messy, future is uncertain." These descriptions captured how they cognitively appraised their condition (experiencing panic attack manifested in hyper arousal, chest tight, stomach is fluttering") with physiological response more or less is in "Alarm stage" of Selye's theory of stress (Campbell et al., 2013).

With regards to the high Positive Relations of the participants, the complicated nature or tendency of social relations requires certain degree of intelligence. Social intelligence as one of the positive psychology constructs, or what is considered as character strength can be included when devising a mental health curriculum. There is a pressing need to increase the level of students' level of environmental mastery which is associated with higher accommodative coping among college students and key to experience life satisfaction in the midst of adversity (Windle and Woods, 2004).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The participants' level of subjective unit of distress is moderate ($X=46.10$); overall well-being is average ($X=55$). The areas or factors considered as "Possible strength" are Positive Relations (5.04) and Personal Growth (5.08) while Personal Acceptance (2.58) and Environmental Mastery (2.76) are the Areas of concern. The null hypothesis is accepted, that is, there is no linear correlation between subjective distress and psychological well-being.

Student Wellness Unit should design an intervention program to improve the participants' Self-acceptance and Environmental Mastery. The educational community should devise ways on how they can help in improving the students' capacity to effectively manage their lives, specifically their academic life.

It was found out that EM is associated with higher accommodative coping and high EM is the key to finding happiness even in the face of adversity (Windle & Woods, 2004 as cited by Perron, 2006). Concerning high score of participants on positive relations, an emerging Social intelligence construct in the positive psychology perspective can be added to further educate students on the need of "intelligence" when relating socially. Social intelligence was discovered to be positively and significantly related to psychological well-being.

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